

SYNTHESIS OF CU-DOPED VANADIUM OXIDE/GRAPHENE HYBRID MATERIAL FOR HIGH PERFORMANCE ELECTROCHEMICAL CAPACITOR

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ABSTRACT

Vanadium oxides have attracted great concern in the research of electrode materials for electrochemical capacitors because of their high theoretical specific capacitance, wide range of sources and low prices. On the other hand, as one of the most promising 2D materials, graphene also gathers much attention during the last decade. In the present work, the vanadium oxide/graphene electrode material for electrochemical capacitors has been successfully synthesized by one-step simultaneous hydrothermal reduction technology, and the Cu-doped modified electrode material has also been prepared by adding cupric nitrate with the same progress. With the investigation of X-ray diffraction pattern (XRD), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and electrochemical measurements, the vanadium oxide/graphene and Cu-doped modified electrode materials both exhibit remarkable electrochemical performance with the starfruit-like structure of vanadium oxide particles in the electrochemical capacitors. High specific capacitances of 193.23F g⁻¹ and 221.90F g⁻¹ have been achieved for vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid material and Cu-doped electrode material respectively in 0.5mol L⁻¹ K₂SO₄ electrolyte at a current density of 0.25A g⁻¹. Moreover, with the modification of the electrode material, the capacitance retention of the hybrid electrode material has increased from 56.27% to 71.79% after a cycling stability test at a current density of 1.0A g⁻¹, showing a good application prospect.

1 INTRODUCTION

Electrochemical capacitors (ECs) have achieved more and more attention during the last few years in energy storage applications for their higher storage capability and power density, compared to conventional capacitors. The extraordinary properties make ECs the most promising devices not only in aerospace but also in civilian field. Up to now, two kinds of ECs have been developed. One is the double-layer capacitors, based on the electric double-layer at the electrode/electrolyte surface, and the other one is the electrochemical pseudocapacitors, relying on the rapid and reversible faradic redox reactions at the surface of electroactive materials [1]. However, deficiency in energy density has become the biggest barrier for ECs' large scale application.

In order to break through the bottleneck of ECs, great efforts have been made. It is well-known that the electrochemical performance of ECs mainly depend on many factors, such as the electrode material and electrolyte, especially, the electrode material. As the research going continuously, two types of ECs electrode materials have been developed, which are carbon-based materials and metallic oxide materials. As for carbon-based materials, the capacitance of which is mainly decided by their specific surface area, making high specific materials like activated carbon [2], activated carbon fiber [3], carbon aerogel [4,5] and carbon nanotube [6-8] the most common candidates for ECs. Hence, although carbon-based materials feature low prices, wide range of sources and advanced techniques, the high manufacturing costs of the materials mentioned before eliminate them from large scale applications. On the other hand, with extremely complicated two and three dimensional structures, metallic oxide materials make highly

reversible redox reactions possible, enabling the efficiently operating of ECs. Currently, metallic oxide materials have been show a promising future, represented by RuO_2 [9, 10], MnO_2 [11], CoO [12], NiO [13], V_2O_5 [14] and so on. However, due to inevitable physical changes during ECs' cyclic operation, for instance density and volume fluctuations, the stability of electrode materials is seriously impacted, even resulting in the detachment of reactive substances. In order to furtherly improve ECs' properties, the notion of metallic oxide/carbon based materials has been promoted, especially the metallic oxide/graphene hybrid electrode materials.

Since been discovered by Geim [15] from 2004, graphene has been attracting many scientists for a decade. As one of the thinnest two dimensional layered materials, graphene show excellent properties in specific surface area, conductivity and mechanics, while its capacitance is somewhat unsatisfactory. For another thing, because of the high theoretical specific capacitance, wide range of sources, low prices and easy synthesis, vanadium has stood out from metallic oxide electrode materials, becoming one of the most promising materials for ECs. Unfortunately, its poor conductivity and instability caused by phase changes driven volume expansion during the cyclic operation are apparent too. Therefore, combining these two kinds of materials together may make the high specific capacitance and long cycle life electrode materials become reality.

In this paper, vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials (RG/VO) and Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials with different graphene amounts were synthesized by one step simultaneous hydrothermal reduction technology. With the high temperature and pressure supplied by hydrothermal technology, starfruit like vanadium oxide particles conjoined with graphene have been achieved. On account of the stable and high specific surface area structure, the prepared materials exhibit desirable electrochemical properties. High specific capacitances of 193.23F g^{-1} and 221.90F g^{-1} have been acquired for vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials and Cu-doped electrode materials respectively in 0.5mol L^{-1} K_2SO_4 electrolyte at a current density of 0.25A g^{-1} . Moreover, with the modification of the electrode material, the capacitance retention of the hybrid electrode materials has increased from 56.27% to 71.79% after a cycling stability test at a current density of 1.0A g^{-1} , showing a good application prospect.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

2.1 Material preparation

GO was manufactured from natural flake graphite (Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Co.) via a modified Hummers method and sequently treated by ultrasonication in order to transform graphite oxide into monolayer graphene oxide. By adding a certain amount of deionized water, GO homogeneous dispersions with different amounts (0.8, 1.2, 1.6, 2.0 and 2.4 mg ml^{-1}) were achieved. Vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials were synthesized as follows: 0.24g NH_4VO_3 powder (Dongfang Chemical Co.) and 20ml deionized water were mixed by vigorous magnetic stirring at 60°C until becoming a suntan transparent solution. Then the NH_4VO_3 solution was added into the as-prepared GO dispersion drop by drop with 10 minutes magnetic stirring. After that, 2.5ml formic acid was added into the mixture with another 10 minutes stirring. Next, the orange liquid was shifted into a 50ml autoclave and heated at 180°C for 12h. At last, the obtained production was refrigerated by water immediately, following by washing and drying at room temperature, and the final product RG/VO was got. Pure vanadium oxide materials were also prepared by the same procedure for contrast. As for the Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials, the synthesis method was similar and the only difference is needing to add a certain amount (5mg and 10mg) of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ into the mixture before shifted into the autoclave with continuous magnetic stirring. All the samples are listed below.

Tags	GO/(mg ml^{-1})	$\text{NH}_4\text{VO}_3/\text{g}$	$\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O} / \text{mg}$
VO	–	0.24	–
RGVO1	0.8	0.24	–
RGVO2	1.6	0.24	–
RGVO3	2.4	0.24	–
RGVOCu1	1.6	0.24	0.005

RGVOCu2

1.6

0.24

0.01

Table 1: Compound design table of all samples

2.2 Chemical physical characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) was performed on a Rigaku D/max 2200PC X-ray diffractometer at the 2θ range of 10 to 80° using Cu K α radiation. The morphology of the hybrid materials was observed via a field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM) system (JEOL 7500F). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to investigate the valence state of vanadium and copper.

2.3 Electrochemical measure

The electrodes were prepared by mixing the obtained product powder, acetylene black and polyvinylidene fluoride in N-methyl-ketopyrrolidine at a mass ratio of 75:20:5. The achieved mixture was then pasted onto half area of a neat nickel foil (1cm \times 2cm) and dried at 110°C for 18h. After that the foil was pressed at 15MPa for about 1 minute becoming a 0.2mm thick slice, following a 4h drying at 110°C and getting the electrode finally. The test for the as-prepared electrodes was operated in a three-electrode system, as platinum foil and saturated calomel electrodes were performed as counter and reference electrodes respectively. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) and galvanostatic charge-discharge measurements were taken to evaluate the electrochemical properties of the vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials and Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1: XRD patterns of GO, VO and RG/VO

The XRD patterns of GO, vanadium oxide and vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials are shown in Fig. 1. From the XRD pattern of GO, it can be seen that the (0 0 2) plane of natural flake graphite (interplanar spacing of 3.35 Å) located at 26.61° is disappeared completely, replacing by an obvious peak located at 10.70° corresponding to an interplanar spacing of 8.26 Å. Hence, it indicates that, with the strong oxidation of concentrated sulfuric acid and KMnO₄, not only the graphite slice surface is anchored by oxygen-containing groups like hydroxy and carboxyl, but also the interlamination of graphite is occupied by hydrones, resulting in the expand of graphite along its c axis and the breakup of its original intact crystal structure. So, under the effect of ultrasound, graphite oxide would be

transformed to graphene oxide naturally. For the as-prepared vanadium oxide and vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials, both of their patterns are perfectly coincided with the V_xO_2 (x between 0.80 and 0.93) with lattice constant $a = 11.72 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 8.96 \text{ \AA}$ and $c = 5.370 \text{ \AA}$, which are corresponding to the (3 1 1), (1 3 0), (4 2 1), (3 0 1), (2 4 2), (2 1 2) and (3 5 0) planes of the V_xO_2 (JCPDS Card File No. 34-0608). Moreover, no diffraction peaks for graphite or other crystals exist, suggesting that the restacking of graphene is suppressed by vanadium oxide particles efficiently and the production purity is high. The intensity of the patterns shows an apparent difference, which means that some impact has been taken on the crystal growth and the prior growth orientation with the addition of graphene, leading to the variation of the XRD diffraction peaks intensity. Therefore, it can be considered as an evidence for the powerful conjunction of vanadium oxide and graphene indirectly.

Figure 2: Comparison among XRD patterns of RGVO2, RGVOCu1 and RGVOCu2

As shown in Fig. 2a, Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials present the similar XRD patterns to vanadium oxide/graphene materials, corresponding to the V_xO_2 as well. However, looking into the patterns carefully, it can be found that two new peak belonging to the (2 2 2) and (0 2 2) planes of $CuVO_3$ (JCPDS Card File No. 26-0568) appear. Besides, c , is promoted in Fig. 2b and 2c. This phenomenon implies that the interplanar spacing of the Cu-doped materials is extended. As the radius of Cu^{2+} , V^{4+} and V^{5+} are 0.73 \AA , 0.58 \AA and 0.54 \AA respectively, when Cu atom is doped into vanadium oxide matrix, the bigger volume needs more spacing and generate a inflation of vanadium oxide crystal, including its lattice planes. All of these indicate a successful synthesis of Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials.

Figure 3: XPS spectra of vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials and Cu-doped hybrid materials: (a) survey spectrum of RG/VO, (b) C1s and (c) V2p respectively; (d) survey spectrum of Cu-doped RG/VO, (e) C1s, (f) V2p and (g) Cu2p, respectively

The valence states of vanadium, oxygen, carbon and copper in the as-prepared electrode materials were further investigated through XPS. From the spectrum of carbon, it can be seen that the majority of carbon are sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms, meaning that the GO has been reduced efficiently during the hydrothermal synthesis process. The V2p core-level spectrum in vanadium oxide/graphene and the Cu-

doped hybrid materials both demonstrate that V^{4+} and V^{5+} ions exist simultaneously. Moreover, the peaks in Cu2p spectrum correspond to Cu^{2+} exactly, agreed with the results from XRD patterns.

Figure 4: SEM images of (a), (b) RG/VO and (c), (d) Cu-doped RG/VO

SEM images were also captured in order to make an observation of the as-prepared vanadium oxide/graphene and Cu-doped vanadium oxide hybrid materials, shown in Fig. 4. In the production of this work, vanadium oxide nanoparticles presented as hexangular starfruit-like morphology and their diameters are in the range of 600nm to 1 μ m, homogeneously distributing on the plate of graphene randomly. When it comes to the Cu-doped materials, the shape and the structure of the nanoparticles or GO changed little. Making a further comparison between them, it is easy to find that the morphology of vanadium oxide particles is more perfect, the little crystal plates among V_xO_2 laminate in Fig. 4b disappear and the diameters of them also shrink to 400nm homogeneously.

In order to evaluate the electrochemical properties, pure vanadium oxide, vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials and Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials with different amount of graphene were investigated by c successively.

The CV curves of VO, RGVO1, RGVO2 and RGVO3 at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ between -0.2 and 0.8 V vs. SCE in 0.5 mol L⁻¹ K₂SO₄ solution are shown in Fig. 5a. Judging from the shape of CV curves, all samples show the similar tracks and deviate from the theoretical rectangle, implying the same electroactive substance V_xO_2 and a remarkable faradic pseudocapacitive characteristic for these electrode materials. Mixing with graphene generate little impact on electrochemical reaction characteristics of electrode materials, showing the analogical fluctuation of CV curves. Nevertheless, samples with graphene promote bigger area compared to samples without it and RGVO2 shows the biggest area, suggesting the highest specific capacity. The results declare that addition of graphene strengthens the electrochemical properties of electrodes.

Based on the formula below and the curves from galvanostatic charge–discharge measurements, the specific capacity for each electrode materials can be calculated exactly.

$$C=It/\Delta Vm \quad (1)$$

In which, ΔV is the difference value of peak and valley for voltage (V), m is the effective mass of

the electroactive substances on electrodes (kg), I is the applied current (A) and t is the time of discharge period (s). Depending on the galvanostatic charge–discharge curves in Fig. 5b, all the specific capacities at for each sample at the current density of 0.25A g^{-1} are achieved in Table 2.

Figure 5: (a) CV curves and (b) galvanostatic charge–discharge curves of VO, RGVO1, RGVO2 and RGVO3

Tags	Unit	Specific Capacity
VO	F g^{-1}	140.02
RGVO1	F g^{-1}	166.88
RGVO2	F g^{-1}	193.23
RGVO3	F g^{-1}	171.48

Table 2: Specific capacities of VO, RGVO1, RGVO2 and RGVO3 at a current density of 0.25A g^{-1}

From Table 2, it can be seen that the same regularity is reflected by CV curves and galvanostatic charge–discharge curves simultaneously, suggesting the promotion of electrochemical properties by adding graphene once again, and it is apparent that RGVO2 exhibits the highest specific capacity of 193.23F g^{-1} . Following few reasons may result in the best specific capacity of RGVO2: (1) Starfruit-like V_xO_2 particles anchored on the surface of graphene restrain the agglomeration and restacking of graphene nanosheets, enlarging the specific surface area and sequently reducing the migration resistance of ions in electrolyte solution by shortening diffusion distance during charge-discharge process. (2) Unique drape structure of graphene nanosheets compensates for volume change of V_xO_2 during phase transition and alleviate the internal stress in electrode materials, improving the structure stability of RG/VO hybrid materials. (3) Extraordinary electrical properties of graphene facilitate the V_xO_2 material in conductivity, making it more suitable for electrochemical capacitor electrode.

Figure 6: (a) CV curves and (b) galvanostatic charge–discharge curves of RGVO2, RGVOCu1 and RGVOCu2

In Fig. 6a, CV curves of RGVO2, RGVOCu1 and RGVOCu2 at a scan rate of 5 mV s^{-1} between -0.2 and 0.8 V vs. SCE in $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution are presented. Similar to Fig. 5a, although doped with copper, the shape of the curves vary little, also showing a remarkable faradic pseudocapacitive characteristic. Besides, judging from the galvanostatic charge–discharge curves, a more excellent electrochemical property is obtained. The explicit specific capacities of RGVO2, RGVOCu1 and RGVOCu2 are listed below in Table 3, based on Fig. 6b.

Tags	Unit	Specific capacity
RGVO2	F g^{-1}	193.23
RGVOCu1	F g^{-1}	208.68
RGVOCu2	F g^{-1}	221.90

Table 3: Specific capacities of RGVO2, RGVOCu1 and RGVOCu2 at a current density of 0.25 A g^{-1}

It can be seen that Cu doping enhances the specific capacity of electrodes furtherly, especially the RGVOCu2 of 0.01g Cu doping reaching 221.90 F g^{-1} .

Current density (A g^{-1})		0.25	0.5	1	2	4
Specific capacity (F g^{-1})	RGVO2	193.2	174.9	159.1	139.8	112.4
	RGVOCu2	221.9	203.6	182.5	152.0	105.6

Table 4: The specific capacities of RGVO2 and RGVOCu2 under different current density

The specific capacities of RGVO2 and RGVOCu2 under different current density are listed in Table 4. When current density increased from 0.25 A g^{-1} to 4 A g^{-1} , the specific capacities of RGVO2 and RGVOCu2 decrease obviously. As the current density increased, the migration of ions in electrolyte speed up. When the migration frequency reach a high level, the electroactive substance inside the electrode will be inactive, resulting in the efficiency and specific capacity decline. Nevertheless, the specific capacity can still reach 110 F g^{-1} approximately, indicating a promising application in high level current density. During the synthesis of the electrode materials, autoclave is cooled down by large amounts of water for rapid cooling, which facilitates the formation of amorphous phase with loose structure. The as-prepared structure is favorable for the rapid adsorption and desorption of ions, generating faradic pseudocapacitive effects and a considerable specific capacity retention.

Figure 7: Cycle stability of RGVO2 and RGVOCu2

Cycle performance is an important requirement for ECs electrode materials. The cycle stability of RGVO2 and RGVOu2 hybrid materials is carried out by repeating the galvanostatic charge–discharge test at a current density of 1.0 A g^{-1} . The capacity retention curves of RGVO2 and RGVOCu2 at a current density of 1.0 A g^{-1} between -0.2 and 0.8 V vs. SCE in $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ K}_2\text{SO}_4$ solution are shown in Fig. 7. It can be seen that after 50 cycles, the capacity retention of RGVO2 and RGVOCu2 are 56.27% and 71.79% respectively and Cu doping improves the cycle performance of electrodes effectively.

In summary, the outstanding electrochemical capacitive performance of RGVOCu2 hybrid materials can be attributed to the following factors: (1) As shown in SEM images, Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials have a more perfect structure and no little crystal plates appear, containing more tunnels for ions migration. Besides, the better integrality strengthen the structure stability of nanoparticles, exhibiting excellent electrochemical properties. (2) Based on the XRD patterns of Cu-doped vanadium oxide/graphene hybrid materials, after Cu doping treatment, part of interplanar spacing is expanded and the atom density is decreased, getting more space for ions migration from electrolyte. Consequently, the capacity retention property is promoted by reducing the effect of charge–discharge process. (3) Extraordinary electrical properties of graphene facilitate the V_xO_2 material in conductivity, making it more suitable for electrochemical capacitor electrode. (4) As for the difference of ionic radius between Cu and V, after Cu doping treatment, there may be solid solution strengthening effect in as-prepared nanoparticles, which can significantly improve the mechanical and stability of electrode materials.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Vanadium oxide/graphene electrode material for electrochemical capacitors has been successfully synthesized by one-step simultaneous hydrothermal reduction technology, and the Cu-doped modified electrode material has also been prepared by adding cupric nitrate with the same progress. Based on various kinds of investigation, the as-prepared materials exhibit remarkable electrochemical properties with the starfruit-like structure of V_xO_2 nanoparticles for electrochemical capacitors. High specific capacitance of 221.90 F g^{-1} has been achieved and the capacitance retention of the hybrid electrode material has increased from 56.27% to 71.79% after Cu coping treatment, showing a good application for energy storage.

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